

Research Article

Analysis of Bumper Designs

Kausalyah Venkatason^{1, *}, Muhammad Muiz Ahmad Mustafa², Shasthri Sivaguru³

^{1,2} School of Mechanical Engineering, College of Engineering, Universiti Teknologi MARA; kausalyah@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9707-0782>)

³ School of Engineering and Physical Sciences, Heriot Watt University Malaysia; s.sivguru@hw.ac.uk; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4076-2010>)

* Correspondence: kausalyah@uitm.edu.my; 6012-4596293.

Abstract: A bumper is a structural component mounted at the front and rear of a vehicle to absorb impact during collisions, playing a crucial role in vehicle safety. Early vehicle bumpers were rigid and primarily ornamental, though they provided some reduction in kinetic energy upon impact. Today, bumper profile design has evolved significantly, with each new design iteration aiming to minimize collision effects more effectively. The inner structure of the bumper, often tailored with specific shapes, is designed to optimize energy absorption and dissipate impact forces. This study aims to analyze existing bumper specifications and profile shapes to identify opportunities for structural improvement across multiple dimensions. Key design adjustments will focus on the bumper's shape and size while maintaining the same material, enhancing strength and impact resistance. Data for optimizing bumper design will be gathered from technical articles and research studies on conceptual design advancements. All design sketches and models will be created using CATIA V5 software, with impact analyses performed in ANSYS 2021 for various bumper profiles under three different controlled collision speeds. The analysis shows that bumper design (A) has the lowest deformation across three different impact speed and has a moderate equivalent Von Mises stress. Thus, this study was able to assess how different profile designs affect collision response and impact reduction, contributing valuable insights into the mechanical optimization of bumper components.

Keywords: vehicle bumper profiles; collision analysis; profile design; speed

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1. INTRODUCTION

A bumper is a component of a car that is located at the front and rear of the vehicle. In consideration of the vehicle's safety systems, it is built to withstand and decrease the amount of impact. The bumper has been designed since 1904 as an improvement to absorb impact during a collision at the same time as a new design for a new vehicle. The automotive bumper is the first component to incur deformation after a collision and plays an essential role in ensuring the structural performance ability of passenger vehicles (Xiao et al, 2015). These are mounted on the vehicle's front and back ends, which are extremely exposed in low-speed or high-speed collisions. It also improves the vehicle's handling and overall performance during the movement.

One of the most difficult problems that the automobile industry is now confronted with is trying to produce cars that are not only safe but also highly fuel-efficient while keeping prices low. Automotive design experts have been faced with a significant difficulty when attempting to include economy, safety, and beauty in their work (Sonawane and Shelar, 2018). Existing automotive vehicle architectures suffer from one basic disadvantage, namely a narrow crumple zone to absorb impact energy. By using bumpers of sufficient quality, it is possible to assure, to a certain extent, the passengers'

safety in the event of a collision involving the vehicle. The bumper protects several different components, including the hood, trunk, grille, fuel, exhaust, and cooling systems, and also a few devices directly connected to safety(Dange et al.,2015). These components may be costly to replace if damaged. In the same vein, this automobile component need not be too heavy in terms of the weight it contributes to the overall rise in the weight of the car. The front or rear bumper of an automobile is the section intended to absorb impact without causing harm to the vehicle's safety systems(Durga,2018).

Dynamic front structure bumper design to accomplish optimal velocity pulses, discuss possibilities to style an adaptive vehicle structure that will change the stiffness in real-time for best energy absorption in a variety of different collision situations. In addition to all of the energy that is absorbed, it is also essential to regulate the intensity throughout the time of the collision. This is because the subsequent crash pulse has a significant impact on the amount of damage that occurs as a consequence of the set velocity of the crash. The performance of impact deformation analysis on three different design variants of automotive bumper beam, observation of the crashworthiness of various shapes of bumper beam, and observation of variation of stress value concerning shape optimization will have a positive impact on the automotive industry. This will be the case because these activities will observe the variation of deformation value concerning shape optimization(Ganesh and Siva, 2020).

2. METHODS & MATERIAL

The method for this analysis is using the ANSYS Workbench 2021 R2 and CATIA V5R21 software that is used for every stage of the research process. This software simulates the bumper beam front end crash against a flat wall to assess the link between velocity and the deformation of the bumper after the impact and the amount of energy absorbed in the crash.

Figure 1. Methodology flowchart

2.1 Model Data Collection

The data for designing the bumper was derived from measurements of an actual bumper and insights from academic journals to define parameters and 3D models. Three bumper designs, all made of aluminum, were used: two were sourced from the Seksyen 7 workshop, and one was based on a low-speed collision study. Each design features a unique cross-sectional profile, allowing for distinct results in impact analysis.

In bumper beam development, cross-sectional design plays a crucial role as it directly influences impact behavior. The interaction between the bumper’s cross-section and impact forces determines the energy absorption capacity of the material. Beyond energy absorption, the cross-sectional profile optimizes structural strength, dimensional stability, and damping capacity, which significantly affect the bumper’s ability to resist bending and absorb energy efficiently. The contribution of cross-sectional design to energy damping and impact resistance surpasses that of many other structural factors (Godara and Nagar, 2019). Table 1 displays the images of the real bumpers where the cross sections were adapted from.

Table 1. Cross-section of the bumper beam

DESIGN	CROSS-SECTION
<p data-bbox="1010 1234 1179 1267">8-type section</p>	
<p data-bbox="1018 1615 1168 1648">0-type section</p>	
<p data-bbox="1015 1921 1168 1955">C-type section</p>	

2.2 3D Modelling

The finest model for the bumpers was obtained through the use of the CATIA V5 R21 program for drawing and designating. The complex form and qualities made this possible. The selection of the parameter was based on the bumper of the real car that was in the workshop. All of the bumpers are the same size, but they differ in shape and cross-section since the impact of the accident may produce different findings for the deformation analysis. The reason for this is that the bumpers are all the same size. The explicit dynamic approach was used to calculate the deformation analysis in ANSYS Workbench 2021 R2. It is commonly known that explicit dynamic techniques outperform implicit ones in the resolution of structural problems involving multiple complex contact interactions that occur over a brief period of time. Because of this, the current study simulates the behaviours of the bumper beam cross-section in the case of a collision with the car using explicit dynamics (Tanlak et al., 2015). It is difficult to perform an impact analysis on a collision when two rigid bodies collide without making contact. In order to assist the anticipated collision, a concrete wall is constructed in Design Modeller within the ANSYS Workbench program for the bumper to contact. Table 2 below shows the general dimensions for the three bumper designs and figures 1 to 4 illustrates the bumper and wall design in CATIA.

Table 2. Design Dimensions

Body	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Height (mm)	Thickness (mm)
Bumpers Design	1150 (mid-point)	50	100	15
Wall	1550	150	500	Solid

Figure 2. Bumper A design.

Figure 3. Bumper B design.

Figure 4. Bumper C design.

Figure 5. Wall design

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By using analysis methods, the dependence of the amount of the vehicle damage on the characteristics of the bumper system in the event of a collision at three different speeds is analyzed and evaluated. The subject of the analysis is a series of experimental collisions conducted under controlled conditions (Gjakovski et.al., n.d). The analysis uses three different parameters which are Bumper A(8-type), Bumper B(0-type), and Bumper C(C-type) using Catia V5 and Ansys software. Below are the deformation and stress plots analysis results.

Figure 6. Deformation and Stress Analysis

This bumper absorbs impact energy by deformation or transfers it perpendicular to the path of impact through the use of a mechanism that can convert approximately 80 percent of the kinetic energy to the spring potential energy in different speed impacts. This occurs regardless of whether the impact is low, medium, or high velocity(Kumar and Pandu, 2013). The stress analysis is the same properties that need to contact the wall but different physical collisions. When the bumper beam is hit from the front, concentrated stresses form on the surfaces, which are placed on the front side that have the same degree of stress(Beyene et.al., 2014).

Figure 7. Graph for maximum deformation

Based on the graph in figure 6, the deformation for all bumpers is increasing when the velocity increase. It's normal when any collision occurs for any bumpers. However, the data shows the highest deformation at 50km/h, 90km/h and 120km/h is bumper C while the lowest deformation is bumper A. This is because the cross-section of bumper C does not have a more solid structure inside the bumper.

Figure 8. Graph for equivalent stress

Figure 8 shows the equivalent stress (von mises) for the three bumpers at three velocities. The stress for bumpers a and c is directly proportional to the increasing velocity of 50m/s to 120m/s. However, bumper b produces the highest stress compared to the other bumpers. This is because

bumper b has a flat surface at the front view without any complex shape. The bumper easily contacts the wall and produces more initial stress when the collision occurs

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, the simulated impact analysis between three types of car bumper models with three different velocities to measure the deformation and internal energy which is stress equivalent (Von Mises), were simulated and analyzed using ANSYS Explicit Dynamic simulation. The car bumper subsystem optimization example is predicated on a general framework for automated crash performance optimization (Farkas et al., 2012). The conclusion was made from the lowest value of maximum deformation and the lower equivalent stress. So, the selected bumper is Bumper A because it has the lowest deformation at maximum impact and medium stress. The parameters for a good bumper need to be added complex shape with a strong structure like Bumper A which has about two combinations of hollow aluminum alloy material. For the recommendation, the Ansys Workbench software needs to be upgraded because it has a limitation to input the high scale data such as mesh that cannot be generated to the smallest size and complex dimension. This will guarantee that parameters with a high level of sensitivity will be considered in the design of the bumper, which will give more positive results of the bumper (Sudin et al., 2007). Ultimately, the study brings together diverse optimization approaches from existing research to evaluate the overall strength enhancements in bumper design, prioritizing improved passenger safety and impact mitigation.

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